

VOLUMETRIC ESTIMATION OF FORMATES BY OXIDATION WITH MERCURIC CHLORIDE

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A specific method, applicable in presence of salts of other organic acids, is described for volumetric estimation of formate ion. The procedure can be adopted for evaluating 10 to 100 mg. of formic acid with a precision of 0.5% or more. The interference caused by other compounds and other organic acids has also been investigated.

Fuchs (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 78, 125) determined neutral alkali formates by titration of the hydrochloric acid liberated during its oxidation with mercuric chloride.

Instead of using an indicator, Fuchs titrated with alkali to the appearance of a yellow precipitate of mercuric oxide. Oldeman (*Pharm. Weekblad.*, 1931, 68, 379) titrated the acid liberated to phenolphthalein end-point after adding an excess of sodium chloride. Bose (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 320) utilised the above reaction for estimating formates by weighing the calomel formed or by titrating the hydrochloric acid after converting the excess of mercuric chloride to K_2HgI_4 . The acidimetric titration to phenolphthalein end-point is interfered by the carbon dioxide liberated, which therefore has to be removed by boiling the solution for a short period. A prolonged boiling, however, drives out a part of the hydrochloric acid also, and consequently low values for the formate are obtained. In the present communication a volumetric method for formate estimation is described which is free from the above interference. The calomel formed is volumetrically estimated in presence of hydrochloric acid (exceeding 4N) by Andrew's method (Jamieson, "Volumetric Iodate Methods", Chem. Catalog Co., 1926) using a standard solution of potassium iodate. The procedure involves the quantitative oxidation of the calomel formed to mercuric chloride by the iodate solution in accordance with the equation :

EXPERIMENTAL

Formic acid, potassium iodate and sodium hydroxide used were of A.R. quality. Sodium acetate and mercuric chloride were of Merck's chemically pure variety. Standard solutions of sodium formate were prepared by neutralising formic acid solutions with 0.1N-NaOH solution in presence of phenolphthalein. A standard solution (0.025 M or 0.1 N) of potassium iodate was prepared by weighing out on a watch glass exactly 5.351 g. of the salt, dried at 120° for one hour, and dissolving it in one litre of water. One c.c. of this solution is equivalent to 23.61 mg. of calomel or 2.3 mg. of formic acid. This solution keeps indefinitely.

Procedure.—A neutral solution (10 to 20 c.c.) of formate containing about 10 to 100 mg. of formic acid was pipetted into a 300 c.c. iodine flask and treated with 5 c.c. of 30% sodium acetate (formate-free) solution and about 25 c.c. of a saturated mercuric chloride solution. The contents of the flask were heated for about 40 minutes by immersing the flask in boiling water. Later the contents were acidified by adding 50 c.c. of HCl (conc.) and cooled by dipping the flask in ice-cold water. The amount of acid added was such that after all the titration liquid had been added, the acidity of the solution in the flask was at least 4 *N*. About 5 c.c. of CCl₄ was introduced into the flask and the contents titrated with iodate solution, taken in a burette, which was run into the flask with constant shaking till the aqueous layer became slightly yellow. At this stage the flask was closed and vigorously shaken, when the CCl₄ layer acquired a purple colour due to iodine. Portionwise addition of KIO₃ in small volumes with shaking was continued till the organic layer was only faintly violet. Then addition was done dropwise with vigorous shaking after each drop till CCl₄ layer lost the last trace of violet colour and had only a very faint yellow tinge due to iodine monochloride. Thus, the end-point of the titration is approached which is clearly perceptible. Excellent results were obtained when shaking was carried out properly and the iodate solution was added slowly. The results for evaluation of different solutions of formate, as recorded in Table I, show that the method has a precision of 0.5% or more. All estimations were carried out in duplicate and the results were quite reproducible. Expts. 1-3 were carried out with the same formate solution with a view to determining the minimum time of heating required for complete oxidation of formate.

TABLE I

[10-20 c.c. formate + 5 c.c. Na-acetate + 25 c.c. saturated HgCl₂, heated in boiling water]

Expt. No.	Time of heating.	HCOONa		% Error.
		Added.	Found.	
1	30 mins.	79.6 mg.	79.9 mg.	+0.4
2	60	"	79.5	-0.2
3	120	"	79.6	Nil
4	40	159.3	160.1	+0.5
5	"	119.5	119.8	+0.3
6	"	63.7	63.8	+0.2
7	"	31.8	31.9	+0.4
8	"	15.9	16.0	+0.6
9	"	7.96	8.0	+0.5

Interferences.—The methods devised for evaluating formic acid by oxidation with mercuric chloride have the advantage of being specifically applicable to formates only, as other carboxylic acids like acetic, propionic, etc. are not oxidised. Therefore the interference caused by salts of various carboxylic acids was investigated with reference to the present modification of the method. The results of expts. 1-11, as recorded in Table II, show that this procedure is not interfered by many organic compounds and salts of carboxylic acids, while those of expts. 12-24 reveal a profound interference caused by aldehydes and some of the salts of organic acids.

TABLE II

[5 c.c. of formate solution + 2 c.c. Na-acetate (30%) + 10 c.c. saturated
 HgCl_2 + substance; heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr].
 Sodium formate added = 39.8 mg.

Expt. No.	Substance added. 0.5 g. (do not interfere)	HCOONa found.	% Error.	Expt. No.	Substance added. 0.2 g. (interfere)	HCOONa found.	% Error.
1.	MeOH	39.9 mg.	+0.3	12.	Salicylaldehyde	49.5 mg.	+25.2
2.	EtOH	40.0	+0.5	13.	Formaldehyde	50.2	+26.2
3.	CCl_4	39.9	+0.3	14.	Acetaldehyde	54.0	+35.2
4.	Benzaldehyde	40.0	+0.5	15.	Glucose	42.3	+6.5
5.	Ca-gluconate	40.0	+0.5	16.	Na-salicylate	71.4	+79.0
6.	„ lactate	40.1	+0.5	17.	„ adipate	41.3	+3.8
7.	„ butyrate	40.0	+0.5	18.	„ malonate	42.5	+6.8
8.	Na-tartrate	40.0	+0.5	19.	„ phthalate	41.3	+3.8
9.	„ citrate	40.0	+0.5	20.	„ aminoacetate	44.5	+12.0
10.	„ benzoate	39.8	± 0	21.	„ phenylacetate	41.7	+4.8
11.	„ borate	39.8	± 0	22.	„ fumarate	42.2	+6.0
				23.	„ maleate	41.7	+4.8
				24.	„ oxalate		Interferes

In conclusion, it may be stated that the procedure described is most suitable among the methods already devised by previous workers for volumetric estimation of formates, using mercuric chloride as an oxidant. The present method affords good and reproducible results as it is free from the interference caused by the formation of carbon dioxide. The end-point with a little practice can be judged very*clearly.

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